

**AUTOMATED FIBER PLACEMENT AND VARIOTHERMAL PRESSING OF
THERMOPLASTIC TOWPREGS**F. Kühn^{1*}, D. May¹, P. Mitschang¹¹ Institut für Verbundwerkstoffe GmbH, Kaiserslautern, Germany*Corresponding author (florian.kuehn@ivw.uni-kl.de)**Keywords:** continuous fiber-reinforced thermoplastics, dry fiber placement, tape placement, variothermal processing, GFRPC**ABSTRACT**

Automated fiber placement offers a high potential to create load-optimized continuous fiber reinforced polymer composites, which is more and more required for high performance composite parts. The possibility of automated fiber placement for thermoplastic composites is currently limited to the processing of fully impregnated and consolidated tapes delivered as a semi-finished product. In order to expand the possibilities for the production of continuous fiber-reinforced thermoplastic composites, a new process chain is developed at IVW using dry rovings and polymer powder in combination with automated fiber placement and direct impregnation. Within this study, the entire process was investigated and process parameters were defined to reduce the pore volume content with high significance using design of experiments with a full factorial experimental plan for the fiber placement and pressing process.

1 INTRODUCTION

The market for fiber reinforced polymer composites (FRPC) has been showing stable and strong growth in recent years, with thermoplastic composites as main growth drivers [1]. With increasing use of these thermoplastic composites, their performance and multifunctionality are becoming more and more important. To exploit the outstanding mechanical properties of the reinforcing fibers, unidirectional fiber structures and load-optimized designs are expedient to achieve maximum performance of the thermoplastic composite components. For the manufacturing of such unidirectional fiber structures the tape placement process, where mostly full impregnated and consolidated semi-finished tapes are processed, is highly suitable. To produce semi-finished tapes, the complex impregnation and consolidation of the roving with the high viscous thermoplastic matrix is outsourced to a separate process. The roving is impregnated either by solvent, melt or powder impregnation [2]. However, these tapes are only available in certain material combinations and configurations (fibers and polymers), which means not every basic material can be used. Thus, the applicability of this flexible process is strongly limited.

In the field of continuous fiber-reinforced thermosets, the dry fiber placement (DFP) has established as a flexible preforming process. The DFP as a modified tape laying process draws back on non-impregnated rovings to produce load-oriented, individual preforms for Liquid Composite Molding. The adhesion of the individual rovings during the fiber placement process is realized by a binder system in small quantities (approx. 3 - 10 wt.%). In a subsequent injection process, the preform is infiltrated with a thermoset matrix [3]. DFP is particularly flexible with regard to the raw materials (rovings), which means that individual and hybrid structures (e. g. steel fiber / carbon fiber parts) can also be produced with minor adaptations of the preforming process [4].

To combine the advantages of thermoplastic tape placement with the flexibility of DFP for the production of continuous fiber-reinforced thermoplastics, a new manufacturing process chain was developed at IVW (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Process chain from the roving and matrix to the consolidated FRPC part

In a first step, the rovings pre-impregnated with thermoplastic powder (TP-powder-towpregs) are produced on roving level where the complete polymer amount required for full impregnation is applied on the roving. In the next step, the TP-powder-towpregs are processed to preforms by fiber placement, whereby the thermoplastic powder takes over the function of a binder (similar to DFP). In a last processing step, the preforms are full impregnated and consolidated within a variothermal pressing process. This process enables the use and combination of low-cost raw materials, whereby the full impregnation of the rovings to consolidated tapes is no longer necessary. Therefore, hybrid components (combination of different roving materials, e. g. GF and steel fibers) can also be produced by this manufacturing process [5].

2 EXPERIMENTS

To gain a comprehensive understanding of the impregnation mechanisms and influences of the processing parameters within the different processing steps on impregnation progress, several test series were carried out at IVW. Particularly, fiber placement and pressing process were examined using design of experiments with a full factorial experimental plan for both processes.

2.1 Materials

For the production of the TP-powder-towpregs, a glass fiber multi-end roving „VETROTEX P185-EC14-2400 tex“ from Saint-Gobain with a titer of 2400 tex was used, whereby the titer was determined experimentally to approx. 2290 tex. This multi-end roving is assembled from different single bundles of fibers and offers a lower internal cohesion compared to single-end rovings, which can lead to an increased formation of gaps during processing. Therefore, this material leads to challenging process conditions (especially for the powder application process) which allows to evaluate the stability of the process chain.

As thermoplastic material the Bayer “Makroblend KU2-7912/4”, a Polycarbonate Polybutyleneterephthalate (PC PBT) blend, with a melting temperature of 223 °C [6] supplied in granular form, was used. For the processing in the new process, the granulate was ground to a grain size mainly in range of 250 µm by Pallmann Maschinenfabrik GmbH & Co. KG. Figure 2 shows particle size distribution and SEM pictures of the PC-PBT powder after the grinding process.

Figure 2: Particle size distribution and SEM pictures of the polymer powder (PC-PBT)

2.2 Powder impregnation

For the production of TP-powder-towpregs a Powder-Supply-Unit and a Powder-Application-Unit, both developed at IVW [3], were used. In a first step the TP-powder is dispensed within the Powder-Supply-Unit (see Figure 3).

Figure 3: Powder-Supply-Unit [3] and Powder-Application-Unit

The TP-powder is stored in a container above a ratchet wheel. This ratchet wheel is driven by a stepper motor and due to adjustable rotation speeds defined and variable powder quantities can be conveyed. An adjustable airstream flows through this unit, takes up the conveyed TP-powder and transports it through a nozzle to the roving within the Powder-Application-Unit in the next step.

Figure 4: Schematic view of the Powder-Application-Unit

Within the Powder-Application-Unit (see Figure 4) the roving is guided inside an aluminum U-profile with a flange distance of 7 mm. This U-Profile serves as a lateral guidance for a calibration of the roving and forces the polymer particles, coming from the Powder-Supply-Unit, to remain on the roving until the heating element is reached. Here, the melting of the polymer particles is realized by a ceramic infrared heating element (IR heater) “Elstein FSR” with a heating power of 1000 W and a wavelength range of 2 - 10 μm . After the roving with the molten TP-particles passed the heating element, the particles cool down, solidify and adhere to the roving. Thus, the TP-powder-towpreg for the fiber placement process is ready to be used.

2.3 Tape placement

For the fiber placement process a tape placement system developed at IVW was used. This tape placement system is suitable for the processing of TP-tapes and bindertapes for DFP as well. It consists of a linear positioning table for a flexible lay-up on a heated tool surface and a tape laying head (see Figure 5).

Figure 5: Tape placement system with tape laying head used for the TP-powder-towpreg placement process

The control of the laboratory tape placement system is computer-assisted, whereby the processing speed of the linear positioning table, the gas mixture of the hot gas torch and the pressure of the compaction roll can be adjusted. The TP-powder-towpreg is guided from a roving spool to the compaction roll within the tape laying head, where the thermoplastic powder is melted by a hot gas torch. A pneumatic cylinder presses the compaction roll onto the heated TP-powder-towpreg at a defined pressure in order to cool, compact and pre-consolidate the TP-powder-towpreg. Thus, the applied powder-towpreg adheres to the lower layers and the preform for the subsequent pressing process is generated according to the specifications.

For the evaluation of the fiber placement process and the influence of the process parameters on the impregnation process the design of experiments with a full factorial experimental plan was used and a statistical evaluation of the results was carried out. The varied parameters for fiber placement were placement-speed of 3 and 6 m/min, hot gas flow rate of 3 and 5 NI/min (affecting the hot gas temperature) and the pressure inside the pneumatic cylinder of the compaction roll of 3 and 4 bar (see Table 1).

Fixed parameter	Value	Varied parameter	Value
Fiber orientation	0°	Placement speed	3 / 6 m/min
Number of layers	6	Compaction roll pressure	3 / 4 bar
Path distance	8 mm	Hot gas amount	3 / 5 NI/min
Heating plate temperature	60 °C		
Compaction roll temp.	40 °C		

Table 1: Parameters for the fiber placement process (DoE with full factorial experimental plan, varied parameter)

2.4 Variothermal pressing process

The variothermal pressing process is used for impregnation and consolidation of the TP-preforms manufactured in the previous tape placement process. For this pressing process, a laboratory hot press developed at the IVW was used (see Figure 6).

Figure 6: Laboratory hot press with pressing tool used for the direct-impregnation process

The control of the press provides the setting of a defined temperature and pressure profile, where a maximum temperature of 800 °C and a maximum force of 5 kN can be set. The maximum heating rate of the heating plates is 10 K/s, the maximum cooling rate is 5 K/s.

The press tool developed and used within this investigation is designed as a plunging edge tool and consists of two identical press bodies and an outer mold ring (see Figure 7).

Figure 7: Design and parts of the pressing tool

The parts of the tool are made of steel (mold ring, and press bodies), the tool cavity has a diameter of 50 mm and a total height of 40 mm.

Within the variothermal pressing process the tool is heated above the melting temperature of the polymer and the processing pressure is applied. The fibers are impregnated with the molten polymer, the mold is cooled down and the impregnated and consolidated part can be removed from the mold.

For evaluating the influence of the process parameters on the impregnation process within the variothermal pressing process the design of experiments with a full factorial experimental plan was used and a statistical evaluation of the results was carried out (similar to the previous tape placement process). The varied parameters for pressing process were tool temperature of 230 and 270 °C, tool pressure of 15 and 20 bar and the pressing time of 2 and 4 min (see Table 2).

Varied parameter	Value
Tool temperature	230 / 270 °C
Tool pressure	15 / 20 bar
Pressing time	2 / 4 min

Table 2: Parameters for the variothermal pressing process (DoE with full factorial experimental plan)

3 RESULTS

The aim of the investigation was to achieve the lowest pore volume content (PVC) within preforming and impregnation process and therefore the highest impregnation progress within tape placement and pressing process. Furthermore, the significant processing parameters for a reduction of PVC were to identify by statistical evaluation of the results of each processing step.

The powder content on the towpreg was to be set to achieve fiber volume content (FVC) of approx. 50% in the final part under assumption that a pore-free impregnation of the rovings can be achieved.

3.1 Production of TP-powder-towpregs

In a first investigation the total amount of powder mass conveyed by the Powder-Supply-Unit at different ratchet wheel rotation speeds was examined (see Figure 8, left).

Figure 8: Conveyed powder mass and applied powder mass on the roving (application on both sides of the roving)

In Figure 8 left it can be seen that the conveyed powder mass is linearly dependent on the ratchet wheel rotation speed, whereby high repeatability of the conveyed powder masses is achieved. Therefore, the selected parameter range allows a stable powder supply without non-linear rotation-speed-dependent factors influencing the powder flow rate. This enables a robust process with high repeatability of the conveyed powder masses and a constant powder flow can be precisely set by adjusting the rotation speed of the ratchet wheel.

In the next step, the powder application on the roving within the Powder-Application-Unit at a roving speed of 1 m/min was investigated (see Figure 8, right). For a homogeneous distribution of the powder particles on the roving and a better stabilization for a good handling of the TP-powder-towpreg the powder was applied on both sides of the roving (double process run), each with a roving speed of 1 m/min and a ratchet wheel rotation speed of 6 rpm. At this ratchet wheel rotation speed a total amount of 0.69 g is conveyed within 60 s. With these settings a mass of approx. 0.55 g powder is applied on each side of the roving. This corresponds to an average powder loss of approx. 20%. With a total powder amount of 1.1 g/m on the roving a FVC of 49.67% in assumption of pore-free impregnation in the final part is achieved.

Figure 9 shows a photography and SEM picture of the TP-powder-towpreg used for further processing within fiber placement process.

Figure 9: TP-powder-towpreg top-view (photography and SEM picture)

The optical evaluation of photography and SEM pictures (Figure 9) show a complete melting of the single particles and good adhesion to the fibers of the GF roving. Furthermore, the particles are distributed homogeneously on the roving and no large agglomerations are visible.

3.2 Preforming by fiber placement process

In this process step, the TP-powder-towpreg was processed by fiber placement to a pre-impregnated and pre-consolidated preform. Figure 10 shows an example of a preform and microscopic images (cross sections) of two preforms with highest and lowest PVC.

Figure 10: Fiber placement preform (left) and optical microscopy images, results with highest (middle) and lowest (right) void-content

In order to prepare the porous preforms for optical microscopy they were embedded under vacuum in an embedding resin to completely fill the pores with embedding resin. This allows preparation of microsections for the subsequent optical analysis where the phases of the embedding resin were treated as quasi-pores. This allows using the PVC of the different preforms as a value for the statistical test evaluation.

Figure 10 middle shows the result with the highest PVC of approx. 70%. The low pre-consolidation and pre-impregnation can already be seen in the photograph. Large parts of the TP-powder-towpreg layers barely adhere to each other with a large number of loose single fibers. The microscopic image reveals the porous structure of this preform. Large areas consist of the embedding resin, respectively the pores within the preform. The processing parameters for the highest PVC were a placement speed of 6 m/min, a compaction roll pressure of 4 bar and a hot gas amount of 3 Nl/min.

In Figure 10, right the sample with the lowest PVC of approx. 28% is shown. This preform is significantly more pre-consolidated than the preform with the high PVC which results in a much more compact and stable preform. The optical microscope image also shows that the share of embedding resin (pores within the preform) is significantly lower. The parameters for the lowest PVC were a placement speed of 3 m/min, a compaction roll pressure of 4 bar and a hot gas amount of 5 Nl/min.

As a result, a targeted influence on the pore volume content is possible and appropriate parameter selection enables the production of compact and stable preforms.

The statistical evaluation of the fiber placement process is shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Results (DoE) for the fiber placement process

Three confidence intervals were calculated according to the DoE. Below 95% there is no indication of difference, between 95 and 99% the results are indifferent, between 99 and 99.9% the results are significant and above 99.9% highly significant.

Figure 11 shows that placement speed and hot gas amount have highly significant effects on the PVC with low placement speed and high hot gas amount having a positive effect for lower PVC. Limiting factors for these parameters are the degradation temperature of the polymer and an economically acceptable fiber placement speed. For compaction roll pressure there is no indication of an influence. The compaction roll pressure only influences the PVC interactively with the hot gas amount (with increasing hot gas amount a high compaction role pressure leads to lower PVC) which has a highly significant effect. The interaction of hot gas amount and placement speed leads only to an indifferent result; the remaining interactions show no indication of difference.

3.3 Impregnation and consolidation by variothermal pressing process

Within the last processing step the fiber placement preforms with the lowest PVC of 28.26% (see Figure 10, right) are processed by variothermal pressing process to full impregnated and consolidated parts. Figure 12 shows microscopic images (cross sections) of two specimens of the test series with highest and lowest PVC.

Figure 12: Optical microscopy images of impregnated and consolidated samples, results with highest (left) and lowest (right) PVC

Figure 12 (left) shows the sample with the highest remaining PVC of 3.37%, the processing parameters were a tool temperature of 230 °C, a pressure of 15 bar, and an impregnation time of 2 min. This sample shows high concentration of pores in the cores of the fiber bundles. These pores indicate that the flow processes, i.e. the impregnation, was not completed. Other indications of an incomplete impregnation process are the large matrix accumulations in different locations of the laminate.

The best result with a remaining PVC of 0.39% (Figure 12, right) was achieved at a tool temperature of 270 °C, a pressure of 20 bar, and an impregnation time of 4 min. This sample shows a significantly more homogeneous distribution of the fiber and matrix areas as well as a lower concentration of pores in the cores of the fiber bundles. The PVC of 0.39% is therefore very low and represents a completely impregnated part.

For the subsequent statistical evaluation and identification of significant effects, the confidence intervals were calculated (95%, 99% and 99.9%). As in the investigation of the tape placement process, a negative effect indicates a reduction of the PVC and thus a better impregnation. An overview of the effects and the confidence intervals are shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Results (DoE) for the variothermal pressing process

Figure 13 shows that all single processing parameters are highly significant for a low PVC and therefore necessary for a good impregnation.

The effect of the interaction between tool temperature and pressure ranges within the confidence interval of 90%. Therefore, this interaction is considered to be independent. Although the individual parameters tool temperature and pressure show highly significant effects, no additional reduction of the PVC can be detected if both factors are increased simultaneously.

The interaction of tool temperature and pressing time shows that the increase of temperature in combination with the increase of time lead to a further reduction of the PVC. The effect exceeds the 99.9% confidence interval and therefore is highly significant.

The effects of the interaction tool pressure and pressing time and the triple interaction tool pressure, pressing time and tool temperature show positive effects (higher PVC) and high significance. This means that a simultaneous increase of the parameters reduces the effect caused by the individual single parameters temperature, pressure and time. This reduction of the effect at triple interaction can be explained by a saturation effect, since linear behavior can no longer be assumed for a low PVC of 0.39%. Therefore, a reduction of the effect at high factor levels of the parameters is plausible.

With regard to an optimal pressing process with high impregnation, it can be summarized that the increase of all single parameters leads to a reduced PVC and therefore to full impregnated and consolidated parts.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The investigation of the new manufacturing process chain shows promising results and a high potential for the production of load-orientated continuous reinforced TP composites. The new developed Powder-Application-Unit enables the production of TP-powder-towpregs, even the processing of multi-end rovings is possible with a constant roving width and without the related gap formation due to the individual fiber bundles within the TP-powder-towpreg. The processing of the TP-powder-towpregs by fiber placement showed that the thermoplastic powder can be used as binder material, comparable to the binder within the dry fiber placement process. It was possible to produce stable and compact preforms for easy handling by fiber placement. The statistical evaluation of the fiber placement process showed a high significance of the parameters placement speed and hot gas amount. Low placement speed and high hot gas amount have a positive effect for a low PVC.

The evaluation of the pressing process showed that all processing parameters are highly significant for a low PVC and therefore for a good impregnation. The best result with a PVC of 0.39 vol.-% was achieved at a tool temperature of 270 °C, a pressure of 20 bar, and an impregnation time of 4 min.

The investigation showed that stable and compact preforms for easy handling can be produced by fiber placement and a full impregnation with a high laminate quality within the pressing process is possible.

The resulting advantages are an universal process, flexible with regard to the input materials and the potential to produce load-orientated and individual hybrid TP composites efficiently.

In next steps, correlations and influences between single process steps will be investigated and guidelines for an optimal overall process with short cycle times and high impregnation quality are derived.

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